

Banking

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Abstract

Banking services are regarded as one of the important service. Banks provide financial services to the customers. Due to the rising competition and liberalization the banking industry has become the buyer's market. Banks need to create and develop the services which can satisfy the consumer needs. Customer satisfaction is a very important construct in today's market and it is directly influenced by service quality as per earliest studies. Therefore, the present research work has been carried out to analyze the rural customers' attitude towards public sector banks

Introduction

The Banking is relationship to customer. The most important requirement for financial institutions like commercial banks is to understand and anticipate customer's needs. The bankers should be aware by keeping themselves at least one step ahead of the customers. With the advancement of information technology and communication system, the whole world has been reduced to a global village. The entry of new generation Private Sector Banks and evolving technology has been changing the face of Indian banking industry. Day in and day out banks deal with customers, be it the depositors or borrowers or anyone who walks into its portals for transacting any business.

In recent years, customers of banking corporations increasingly use technology and direct channels to consume banking services. This phenomenon is also evident worldwide. Expanding E-Banking services and the types of services including banking via the Internet, telephone and using Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), makes it possible to reduce the prices of services to customers, and makes it easier for them to manage their activity independently and conveniently anywhere, at any time, through various channels, and regardless of the working hours of the branches of their banking corporation.

Objectives

- Role of Banks in Economic Development
- GST and banking
- Customer Service Important
- Types of Bank in India
- Retail Banking
- E-Banking
- Modes of Distribution

- Automated Teller Machine
- Online Tax Payment
- Conclusion
- Reference

Role of Banks in Economic Development

In a developing country like India, there are many factors that hinder the development of the country. Some of them can be endorsed to the low per capital income and large group of people living below the poverty line. India is an agrarian economy where the country's potential, neither the human resource nor the natural resources are adequately utilised to the maximum extent which results in low per capital income. Besides the reasons mentioned above, the financial market was in the presence of Private Money Lenders, Landlords, etc.. Thus, the importance of commercial banks in the process of economic development has been pointed out regularly by economic thinkers and policy makers of the country. Commercial banks played an important role in the Indian economy and considered as the heart of the financial structure.

GST and Banking

Transaction fees in financial services are likely to increase as the government has put these under the 18% tax bracket in the new GST regime. These services were so far taxed at 15% and the hike in the tax rate means that individuals will have to pay Rs 3 more for every Rs 100 paid as charges/ fees for banking transactions. It may be mentioned that recently several banks starting with SBI introduced or increased service charges for multiple banking transaction.

Customer Service Important

- Changing customer expectations: Today the customer is more demanding and more sophisticated than he or she was thirty years ago.
- The increased importance of customer service: With changing customer expectations, competitors are seeing customer service as a competitive weapon with which they differentiate their products and services.
- The need for a relationship strategy: To ensure that a customer service strategy that will create a value proposition for customers should be formulated implemented and controlled. It is necessary to give it a central role and not one that is subsumed in the various elements of the marketing mix.
- Types of Bank in India

Public Sector Banks in India

S. No.	Bank Name	Head Quarter/Office	Tagline
1	State Bank of India	Mumbai	The Nation banks on us; Pure Banking Nothing Else; With you all the way
2	State Bank of Bikaner	Rajasthan	
3	State Bank of Hyderabad	Hyderabad	You can always bank on us
4	State Bank of Mysore	Bangalore	Working for a better tomorrow
5	State Bank of Patiala	Punjab	
6	State Bank of Travancore	Thiruvananthapuram	A Long Tradition of Trust

Other Nationalized Banks

S.No.	Bank Name	Head Quarter/Office	Tagline
1	Allahabad Bank	Kolkata	A tradition of trust
2	Andhra Bank	Hyderabad	Where India Banks
3	Bank of Baroda	Vadodara	India's International Bank
4	Bank of India	Mumbai	Relationships beyond Banking
5	Bank of Maharashtra	Pune	One Family One Bank
6	Canara Bank	Bangalore	Together we Can, It's easy to change for those who you love
7	Central Bank of India	Mumbai	Central to you since 1911, Build A Better Life Around Us
8	Corporation Bank	Mangalore	A Premier Public Sector Bank, Prosperity for all
9	Dena Bank	Mumbai	Trusted Family Bank
10	Indian Bank	Chennai	Your Tech-friendly bank
11	Indian Overseas Bank	Chennai	Good people to grow with
12	Oriental Bank of Commerce	Gurugram	Where every individual is committed
13	Punjab National Bank	New Delhi	The Name you can Bank Upon
14	Punjab & Sind Bank	New Delhi	Where series is a way of life
15	Syndicate Bank	Manipal	Faithful. Friendly
16	UCO Bank	Kolkata	Honours Your Trust
17	Union Bank of India	Mumbai	Good people to bank with
18	United Bank of India	Kolkata	The Bank that begins with "U"
19	Vijaya Bank	Bangalore	A friend You can Bank Upon
20	IDBI Bank Ltd	Mumbai	Banking for all; "Aao Schein Bada"
21	Bharatiya Mahila Bank	New Delhi	Empowering women, Empowering Ind"

Retail Banking

"Retail Banking" encompasses mutual funds, debit cards, credit cards, retail deposit schemes, retail loans, insurance products, depository services including demat facilities and a host of other services catering to the needs of the individual customers.

E-Banking

Electronic banking can be defined as the use of electronic delivery channels for banking products and services, and is a subset of electronic finance (1). The most important electronic delivery channels are the Internet, wireless communication networks, automatic teller machines (ATMs), and telephone banking. Internet banking is a subset of e-banking that is primarily carried out by means of the Internet. The term transactional e-banking is also used to distinguish the

use of banking services from the mere provision of information. After few years down the line, they transformed their websites from only informational websites to dynamic transaction- oriented websites that are providing ‘anytime anywhere’ banking services.

Role of Customer Using E-Banking

Customers can access Any Bank.com only by using their User ID and Password. During the first login attempt, it is mandatory to change both passwords - login and transaction – which would have been mailed to customer by the bank. If customers forget their password, they will have to write to bank using the “Email Us” option. The Bank will then issue a new password and send it to their mailing address as per bank’s records.

Modes of Distribution

- Internet Banking
- Tele-phone Banking
- Plastic Banking
- **Internet Banking:** It is also known as Web Banking or PC Banking or e-Banking. The easy accessibility to internet facility and availability of computer lead the banks to provide their products and services through new delivery medium i.e. internet. Today, all private and public sector banks are providing e-banking services to their clients.
- **Tele-Phone Banking:** It is also known as Phone Banking or Mobile- Banking or M- Banking. India has experienced tremendous increase in the number of mobile phone users. The rate of penetration of mobiles and landlines has risen significantly and this leads to encourage banks to grab this opportunity and thus offered mobile- banking services. Through this service customers can avail information regarding the bank account by sending a SMS.
- **Plastic Money:** It is referred to ATM cards, debit cards and credit cards etc. Banks have provided ATM facility to their customers and it is connected via V-SAT. Through using ATM, customers can avail a numerous services, such as, withdrawal of funds, account balance enquiry, order a cheque book, deposit fund, have information regarding banking products etc. Even through ATM banks are offering value added services also.

Book Ticket Online

With Bank customers need not to visit booking reservation centres to book their travel tickets. Customers can now buy their train tickets online and pay using Bank’s Internet Banking Facility. All internet banking customers can use this facility.

Funds Transfer (e-Cheques)

Now, with Any Bank.com, transferring funds from Bank Account is very simple. There are various options provided online for transferring funds on Bank’s website. Customers can select to:

- (i) Transfer Funds to their own linked Bank accounts
- (ii) Transfer Funds to other Bank accounts, anywhere in India
- (iii) Transfer Funds to specified Non-Bank accounts

Automated Teller Machine

ATM stands for automated teller machine. An automated teller machine (ATM) is an electronic banking outlet that allows customers to complete basic transactions without the aid of a branch representative or teller. Anyone with a Credit card and Debit card can access most ATMs. The first ATM appeared in London in 1967, and in less than 50 years, ATMs had spread around the

globe, securing a presence in every major country and even tiny little island nations such as Kiribati and the Federated States of Micronesia. ATMs are part of one or more networks, such as 1□link, M-Net etc. An ATM card can be used in one of these machines. An ATM card has a magnetic strip that contains a unique card number and some security information. It can be used at ATM for deposits, withdrawals, account information, and other types of transactions.

Benefit of ATM Cards

ATM card transactions are generally processed immediately in the electronic banking system, so your bank balance will reflect the debit as soon as the transaction is complete. The system can determine whether your account has a sufficient balance to pay for the transaction, thus guarding against an accidental overdraft.

Debit Card

A debit card can be used in place of using a credit card or cash or a cheque to pay for merchandise. Debit card also allows for instant cash withdrawal, acting as an ATM card. In many banks, the two functions of ATM card and credit card are combined into a single debit card.

Benefit of Debit Cards

Since debit cards work like credit cards, they can be used online and for catalog purchases or Transactions made over the telephone, as well as those made in person. These types of transactions are typically free of any banking fees charged to the owner of the bank account. Moreover, a debit card uses checking account of the customer instead of adding to his credit card debt.

Online Prepaid Mobile Recharge

Customers can recharge Prepaid Mobile from the comfort of home or office, anytime, anywhere with Prepaid Mobile Recharge Facility on Any Bank.com.

Now customers no longer need to rush to the vendor for buying recharge cards, every time their talk time runs out. This service is absolutely free for all Bank Account holders.

Advantages of E-Banking

- Customer's account is extremely accessible with an online account.
- Customer can withdraw cash at any time through ATMs that are now widely available throughout the country.
- Besides withdrawing cash customers can also have mini bank statements, balance inquiry at these ATMs.
- Through Internet Banking customer can operate his account while sitting in his office or home.
- The Growth of credit card usage also owes greatly to E-banking. Now a customer can shop worldwide without any need of carrying paper money with him.
- Banks are available 24 hours a day, seven days a week and they are only a mouse click away.

Disadvantages of E-Banking

- If the bank's server is down, customer can't use it.
- To use internet banking, customer is compelled to have computer with internet access.
- There is always the possibility of a cracker gaining access to customer's account.
- Many banks don't show customer how to use online banking very well and those are usually the ones with the non-intuitive interface & cluttered design, which makes it pretty easy for

customer to screw up something.

- Banks bears heavy costs to install high firewall.
- It leads to missing of personal services.
- E-banking promotes lack of socializing or social contacts

Online Tax Payment

Pay Direct Tax and Indirect Tax Online

Customers can pay their Direct or Indirect Tax Online in 7 easy steps:

1. Tax payers to select the relevant challan from NSDL site.
2. Taxpayers to enter their PAN / TAN / Assessee code as applicable. There will be an online check on the validity of the PAN / TAN / Assessee code entered.
3. If PAN/ TAN/ Assessee code is valid the taxpayer will be allowed to fill up other challan details like accounting head code / Major head code under which payment is made, name and address of PAN/TAN and also select ICICI Bank through which payment is to be made.
4. On submission of data entered a confirmation screen will be displayed. If the taxpayer confirms the data entered in the challan, it will be directed to the net-banking site of ICICI Bank.
5. The taxpayer will login to the ICICI Bank internet-banking site with the User id/ Password provided by the ICICI Bank (Retail Internet Banking).
6. Taxpayer to enter payment details and authorize the payment.
7. On successful payment a challan counterfoil will be displayed containing CIN, payment details and Bank name through which e-payment has been made. This counterfoil is proof of payment being made.

Customers can also log in to download their Direct or Indirect Tax payment acknowledgment for last three months of payments made through Bank.com from e Tax challan link in Bank Accounts section.

Following Taxes Can Be Paid Through Online Tax Service

- Tax Deducted at Source
- Income Tax
- Corporation Tax
- Security Transaction Tax
- Hotel Receipts Tax
- Estate Duty
- Interest Tax
- Wealth Tax
- Expenditure Tax
- Gift Tax
- Banking Cash Transaction Tax
- Fringe Benefits Tax
- Indirect Tax - Central Excise Tax
- Indirect Tax - Service Tax

Challenges of Internet Banking

Challenges of E- Banking are as follows

1. Demand side pressure due to increasing access to low cost electronic services.
2. Emergence of open standards for banking functionality
3. Global players in the fray

Threats of Internet Banking

The Threats of e-Banking are as follows

1. The Most common way of hoaxing with the information is the cracking login and passwords of e- banking users.
2. Denial of services: high trafficking of queries result into jamming computer network.
3. Data Diddling: Information and data can change in an unauthorized way. It can result in receiving higher amount bill rather than actual amount to be paid by customers.

Conclusion

Ranking and brand value of some Indian banks raised recently. Banking business over the period of time has increased. Number of bank offices / bank branches and number of employees have increased. Recently the number of employee is decreasing due to more adaptation of technology in the banking sector. Further, the amount of deposit, credit and investment in the government projects is increasing over the period of time. Advances to priority sector are also exhibiting the growing trend. It is observed that deposit and branch; total business and branch; total business and deposit; and total business and credit are found to be highly correlated. There is a strong positive correlation between the above stated pairs.

E-Banking has transformed not only the banking relationships but transformed the whole banking industry. The e- banking, therefore taken as a mandate by the banks rather than just an additional feature in most of the developed nations, as it is the economical medium to cater the banking customers. Through e- banking, customers can process any banking transaction without even visiting bank branch at any time anywhere and this is known as “anywhere banking”. Providing e- banking is no more considered as an additional feature of a banking institution, but now it is became an essential feature of a bank.

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